

enedioxy protons. Two aromatic protons, C_7-H and $C_{11}-H$ appeared as two sharp singlets at δ 7.46 and 7.33, respectively.

It is quite interesting that 4 on treatment with ethanolic hydrochloric acid gas underwent retrogression to give rise to 1 and 2. The retrogression could be represented as in Scheme 2.

Scheme 2

Reagents: 1, OH^- , ketonisation.

Attempts to cyclise 5 to get 7 by refluxing in ethanol for 15 h did not materialise. However, efforts are on way to cyclise 5 by using different catalysts.

Experimental

Compounds were routinely checked for their homogeneity by tlc on silica gel G. Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a Varian EM-390 90MHz spectrometer using TMS as internal reference.

Methyl-6-[3,4-dihydro-4,4,6-trimethyl-2-thioxo-1-(2H)pyrimidinyl]-1,3-benzodioxole-5-carboxylate (4):

Method A: Methyl-6-aminopiperonylate⁸ (1; 1.95 g, 0.01 mol) and 2-methyl-2-isothiocyanopentan-4-one⁹ (2; 1.57 g, 0.01 mol) were mixed together and heated on a steam-bath. Initially the contents became mobile but as the reaction proceeded the mass became solid. After heating it for 3 h, the product was cooled and crystallised from ethanol (1.84 g, 55%), m.p. 192° (Found: C, 57.28; H, 5.47; N, 8.21. $C_{16}H_{18}N_2O_4S$ requires C, 57.49; H, 5.39; N, 8.38%).

Method B: To a solution of 1 (0.195 g, 0.001 mol) in ethanol (5 ml) was added 2 (0.16 g, 0.0011 mol). After keeping for 5 days at room temperature (25-30°), the compound separated was filtered under suction and crystallised from ethanol (48%), m.p. 192°. It was found to be the intermediate 4 identical in all respect with the compound obtained by Method A.

1,3,3-Trimethyl-3H,6H-[1,3]dioxolo[4,5-g]pyrimido[1,2-a][3,1]benzothiazin-6-one (6): A solution of 4 (3.34 g, 0.01 mol) in dry benzene (100 ml) was added dropwise to freshly prepared sodium ethoxide in the same solvent (20 ml) with continuous stirring at room temperature. The turbidity increased as the addition progressed. After the completion of addition, the contents were refluxed over a steam-bath for 8 h. Benzene was distilled off and the residue was dissolved in water and filtered. The filtrate on

acidification with acetic acid furnished the product 6 which was collected under suction, dried and crystallised from ethanol, (2.26 g, 75%), m.p. 227° (Found: C, 59.78; H, 4.43; N, 9.39. $C_{18}H_{14}N_2O_5S$ requires C, 59.60; H, 4.64; N, 9.27%).

Methyl-6-[(4,4,6-trimethyl-4H-1,3-thiazin-2-yl)amino]-1,3-benzodioxole-5-carboxylate (5): A mixture of 1 (0.195 g, 0.001 mol) and 2-mercapto-4,4,6-trimethyl-1H,4H(1,3) thiazine⁴ (8; 0.173 g, 0.001 mol) was heated on an oil-bath at 100° for 8 h and then the temperature was raised to 120° for 3 h. At this temperature the evolution of H_2S practically ceased. After cooling, the product was crystallised from carbon tetrachloride, yield (0.2 g, 60%), m.p. 95-6° (Found: C, 57.24; H, 5.54; N, 8.52. $C_{16}H_{18}N_2O_4S$ requires C, 57.49; H, 5.39; N, 8.38%. ν_{max} 3120 (NH) and 1665 cm^{-1} ($-CO-O-CH_3$); δ ($CDCl_3$) 8.56 (1H, bs, NH exchangeable with D_2O), 7.30 (1H, s, C_4-H Ar), 6.21 (1H, s, C_7-H Ar), 5.93 (2H, s, OCH_2O), 5.53 (1H, s, $-CH=$), 3.86 (3H, s, $COOCH_3$), 1.93 (3H, s, $=C-CH_3$), 1.43 (6H, s, $=C(CH_3)_2$).

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Chemical Constituents of *Allanthur grandis* Prain

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THE isolation and characterisation of two quassinoids, viz. 6 α -tigloyloxyparrin and 6 α -tigloyloxyparrinone from the bark of *Allanthur grandis* Prain have been reported earlier¹. A complete report on the chemical constituents of the same

is lacking and hence, we wish to report in this note the other chemical constituents present in the bark of *Ailanthus grandis*.

During our study for isolation of the quassinoids we initially collected the plant growing at various altitudes ranging from the foothills to a height of 5000 ft in the district of Darjeeling. It was found that mannitol and not the quassinoids was present in the bark of the plant collected from the higher altitudes above 1000 ft, whereas the sterol, lupeol, α -amyrin and betulenolic acid were isolated in all the cases.

Experimental

The powdered bark of *Ailanthus grandis* was extracted with benzene in a Soxhlet apparatus for 36 h. A heavy crystalline solid appeared at the end of the extraction and was separated from the benzene extract by filtration. The residue was washed with CHCl_3 and then crystallised from water-ethanol mixture to furnish crystalline solid, m.p. 165-66° that was analysed for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_6$; NaOAc-Ac₂O acetylation of which furnished acetate, m.p. 113-120°; $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_{12}$; $[\alpha]_D + 25^\circ$ that was found identical with mannitol hexaacetate by m.m.p. and co-tlc with an authentic sample.

The solvent from the benzene extract was distilled under reduced pressure and the gummy residue was separated into neutral and acid parts. The neutral part was chromatographed over deactivated alumina. Elution with petroleum ether-benzene (4:1) gave a solid which on crystallisation from CHCl_3 -MeOH furnished silky crystals, m.p. 213-14°; $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$, M^+ 426; $[\alpha]_D + 26^\circ$; ν_{max} 3330, 3040, 1640 and 885 cm^{-1} ; treatment with Py-Ac₂O furnished an acetate, m.p. 220-22°, $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_2$, $[\alpha]_D + 48^\circ$, identical with lupenyl acetate².

The chromatogram on further elution with petroleum ether-benzene (3:2) yielded a solid, m.p. 186-88°, $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$, M^+ 426; $[\alpha]_D + 90^\circ$; acetylation (Py-Ac₂O) gave an acetate, m.p. 225-26°, $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_2$, M^+ 468, identical (m.m.p., co-ir and co-tlc) with an authentic sample of α -amyrin acetate³. The column on further elution with petroleum ether-benzene (2:3) yielded a crystalline solid, m.p. 136-37°, $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$; $[\alpha]_D - 34^\circ$ which was identified as β -sitosterol by direct comparison with an authentic sample (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir).

The acid part was esterified (CH_3N_2) and the solid chromatographed over deactivated alumina. The solid obtained on elution with petroleum ether-benzene (3:2) was crystallised to furnish a solid, m.p. 222-24°; $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_3$, M^+ 470; $[\alpha]_D + 4^\circ$; ν_{max} 3560, 3140, 1715, 1660 and 885 cm^{-1} . The solid on acetylation (Py-Ac₂O) yielded the ester acetate, m.p. 202-203°; $\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_4$, M^+ 512; $[\alpha]_D + 17^\circ$ which was found identical (m.m.p., co-ir and co-tlc) with an authentic sample of acetyl methyl-betulanate⁴.

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Further Constituents of *Adenia cissampeloides*

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ADENIA cissampeloides (Passifloraceae) is a climber that can grow to 12 cm in diameter. It grows in humid areas of West Africa. Medicinally, it is used in Southern Nigeria as a remedy for lumbago. In Ghana, the leaves are rubbed on the breasts after child birth to promote lactation. It is used in Southern Nigeria and Ghana as a powerful fish poison (as with *A. lobata*). In a previous paper¹, cyanogenesis and the occurrence of tetraphyllin B, which readily hydrolyses to 4-hydroxy-2-cyclopentenone with liberation of hydrogen cyanide gas, was reported. The paper also discussed the isolation of friedelan-3 β -ol, friedelan-21-one and β -sitosterol from the stem. The present paper which concentrates on the more polar constituents of this species reports on the isolation of mannitol sucrose and sodium chloride.

Experimental

Adenia cissampeloides was collected from Ojoo in Ibadan and identified by the Federal Department of Forestry Research where a voucher specimen No. FHI 91470 is deposited.

Isolation of sucrose: Fresh *A. cissampeloides* stem (1 kg) was defatted with light petroleum and extracted with methanol-acetone mixture (1:1) in cold for 48 h. This was concentrated under reduced pressure and partitioned between ether and water. The water fraction was rotavapoured at 30° to a syrup and chromatographed over deactivated silica. Ether-methanol (1:1) eluted a reddish yellow syrup which on rechromatography afforded a solid, recrystallised from methanol (162 mg), m.p. 181-183°.